

Development of a Height-Tapered Double Cantilever Beam Test Method for Mode I Interlaminar Fatigue Testing

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Motivation

Importance of Delamination and Mode I Failure in Composite Laminates

- Delamination is one of the most critical failure modes in laminated composite structures.
- It is often visually undetectable, making it highly dangerous and difficult to monitor.
- Leads to a significant reduction in both stiffness and strength.
- Fatigue-induced delamination is: Hard to detect; Irreversible; performance degradation or even catastrophic failure
- Design Philosophies in Practice:
 - No-Delamination Growth Principle (Conservative approach)
 - **Damage Tolerance Philosophy** (widely recommended): Emphasizes understanding failure mechanisms; Requires accurate prediction and monitoring tools
- In 2009, the Federal Aviation Administration (FAA) introduced '**slow growth**' **approach** to the certification of composites
- Among delamination modes, Mode I (opening mode) is often most critical.
- Dominates early-stage crack initiation in fatigue

Progression of crack

**Single Step Lap Joint Failure:
Combination of Mode-I and Mode-II Loading**

Challenges in Traditional Mode-I Fatigue Testing Methods

- Traditional Mode-I fatigue testing methods - based on constant load range (ΔP) or displacement range (Δd) - fail to maintain constant ΔG
- Under load control, ΔG increases with crack growth, leading to instability ($da/dN \rightarrow \infty$)

$$\Delta G = \frac{(P_{\max}^2 - P_{\min}^2)a^2}{bEI}$$

- Conversely, under displacement control, ΔG decreases with increasing crack length, resulting in crack arrest ($da/dN \rightarrow 0$)

$$\Delta G = \frac{9EI}{4ba^4} (\delta_{\max}^2 - \delta_{\min}^2)$$

G-controlled Mode I Fatigue Testing

Russell & Street, 1988: A Constant ΔG Test for Measuring Mode I Interlaminar Fatigue Crack Growth Rates

FIG. 1—Experimental arrangement for constant ΔG interlaminar fatigue.

- Double Cantilever Beam (DCB) specimen loaded in series with a linear elastic spring.
- Spring mechanism provides optimum control of energy release rate (ΔG) during fatigue crack propagation.
- Displacement-controlled cyclic loading.

Manca et al., 2015: G-control fatigue testing for cyclic crack propagation in composite structures

- **Computer-controlled G-control testing** methodology
- Displacement-controlled fatigue

$$\Delta G = \frac{9EI}{4ba^4} \delta_{max}^2 (1 - R^2)$$

Arhant et al., 2021: Fatigue crack growth properties of carbon-polyamide 6 thermoplastic composites using a multi- ΔG control method

From Manca et al. [12]

This study

G-controlled Mode I Fatigue Testing

Research Gaps

1. *Frequent adjustment of displacement in the standard DCB fatigue testing to keep ΔG constant*
2. *Even small increments in crack length can cause significant changes in ΔG*
3. *Lack of Consideration for R-Curve Effects; difficult to understand the R-curve effect with standard DCB*
4. *The influence of R-curve behavior on the accuracy and reliability of Paris law fitting remains poorly understood.*

Geometry-Based G-controlled Mode I Quasi-Static Testing

- Achieve constant ΔG during crack growth by altering the geometry of standard DCB
- ASTM Standard Available for HTDCB of Adhesively Bonded Metal Joints
- No standard available to perform **fatigue HTDCB testing**
- **No comprehensive guidance exists** for designing HTDCB specimens specifically for fatigue testing of composite materials
- Prior studies focused exclusively on **Quasi-static behavior of adhesively bonded metal-metal or Wood**, with no application to composite laminates.

ASTM D3433: Standard Test Method for Fracture Strength in Cleavage of Adhesives in Bonded Metal Joints

Objective of This Study

- Designing Height-Tapered DCB (HTDCB) specimen to **maintain a constant energy release rate (G) and load (P)** during **quasi-static** delamination testing
- HTDCB configuration effectively maintains a **constant G** during **fatigue loading** conditions
- Ensure **stable crack growth** throughout fatigue testing
- Obtain **sufficient crack length** to accurately calculate fatigue crack growth rate (da/dN)

Design of HTDCB for Mode I Fatigue Testing of Composites

- **Shear flexible Timoshenko beam** is described through the following two differential equations:

$$\text{Moment, } M(x) = EI \frac{d\phi_z(x)}{dx} = Px$$

$$\text{Shear force, } V(x) = k_s AG \left(\frac{dy}{dx} - \phi_z(x) \right) = -P$$

For classical Euler–Bernoulli formulation, $k_s AG = \infty$; shear-rigid beam

Here, P = Load, E = Flexural modulus, I = Moment of inertia, k_s = Shear correction factor, A = cross-sectional area, $\phi_z(x)$ = *cross-sectional rotation*, y = deflection

$$\frac{d\phi_z(x)}{dx} = \frac{Px}{EI}$$

$$\frac{dy}{dx} = -\frac{P}{k_s AG} + \phi_z(x)$$

Deflection equation, $y(x)$, was obtained by solving the two equations with the applied boundary conditions, $\phi_z(a) = 0$ and $y(a) = 0$

$$h_L = h_o + \alpha a$$

$$\tan \theta = \frac{h_L - h_o}{a} = \alpha$$

$$k = \frac{\alpha}{h_o}$$

Design of HTDCB for Mode I Fatigue Testing of Composites

- **Timoshenko Beam Theory**, deflection, and compliance equations were analytically derived, accounting for both **flexural and shear effects**
- **Linear elastic fracture mechanics**-based strain energy release rate (**SERR**) equation (G) was derived
- **Validated** against **ASTM D3433-99** for metal joints (Poisson's ratio = 1/3)

- **Deflection at loading point, $y(x = 0) = \delta$**

$$\text{Deflection, } \delta = \frac{Pa(-2 - 3ka)}{EI_0k^2(1 + ka)^2} + \frac{2P \log(1 + ka)}{EI_0k^3} + \frac{2P}{A_0G} \frac{\log(1 + ka)}{k}$$

$$C = \frac{\delta}{P}$$

$$\text{Compliance, } C = \frac{a(-2 - 3ka)}{EI_0k^2(1 + ka)^2} + \frac{2 \log(1 + ka)}{EI_0k^3} + \frac{2}{A_0G} \frac{\log(1 + ka)}{k}$$

$$G_I = \frac{P^2 dC}{2b da}$$

$$\text{SERR, } G_I = \frac{12P^2a^2}{Eb^2h_0^3(1 + ka)^3} + \frac{P^2}{k_sGb^2h_0(1 + ka)}$$

Rearranging Equation

$$G_I = \frac{4P^2}{Eb^2} \left[\frac{3a^2}{h_L^3} + \frac{3E}{8Gh_L} \right]; \text{ Equation similar to ASTM D3433}$$

$$G_I = \frac{4P^2}{Eb^2} \left[\frac{3a^2}{h_L^3} + \frac{1}{h_L} \right]; \text{ ASTM D3433 Equation}$$

Geometry-Based Approaches to Maintain Constant ΔG During Mode-I Fatigue Testing

- Three approaches available to achieve constant ΔG during crack growth by altering the geometry of standard DCB

Parametric Study Varying Tapered Angle of HTDCB

— Angle = 0.001 Deg — Angle = 1 Deg — Angle = 2.5 Deg
 — Angle = 4 Deg. — Angle = 5 deg — Angle = 6 Deg
 — Angle = 7.5 deg — Angle = 10 Deg

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- Parametric analysis** varying the tapered angle (α) from 0° to 10° identified a **5° taper** with an initial crack length of **75 mm**

Parametric Study Varying Tapered Angle of WTDCB

- Performed parametric analysis on Width-Tapered DCB (WTDCB) specimens by varying the taper angle from 0° to 45°
- Found that a taper angle of **at least 45°** is necessary to maintain a constant G with an initial crack length of **~80 mm**
- Such large taper angles lead to a **beam-to-plate transition**, complicating specimen geometry and testing
- Consequently, the **HTDCB configuration** was selected for further investigation

HTDCB Geometry to Maintain Constant ΔG During Mode-I Fatigue Testing

Analytical equation indicates ΔG remains independent of crack growth during fatigue testing

Materials and Methodology

- 463 S-glass Plain Weave Fabric
- RDL-RDC-Epoxy Resin
- Vacuum Assisted Resin Transfer Molding (VARTM) at 60 °C
- Curing: 80°C for 2.5 hrs and 121°C for 4 hrs
- Flexural Modulus: ~ 20 GPa
- Shear Modulus: ~ 2.5 Gpa
- **16-layer PW-RDL-RDC composite** with a pre-crack length of 100 mm at the mid-plane using a Teflon film

HTDCB Quasi-Static Testing

HTDCB Test Setup

Image processing software, Fiji ImageJ, used to measure the crack propagation distance

- Quasi-static tests were conducted at two displacement rates (**0.2 mm/min** and **0.5 mm/min**) to assess rate effects.
- No rate dependence was observed within this range.

HTDCB Quasi-Static Test Result

- **Load increases** during the initial ~20 mm of crack growth, indicating **R-curve behavior**.
- **Load stabilizes** once fracture toughness reaches the **plateau region**.
- Design equation was developed assuming **constant fracture toughness**.
- R-curve behavior attributed to mechanisms such as **fiber bridging, tow-to-tow delamination, and secondary cracking**.

Experimental Results

Analytical Prediction

HTDCB vs Standard DCB Quasi-Static Test Result

- Fracture toughness (G_{IC}) vs crack growth (Δa) compared
- HTDCB demonstrated **R-curve behavior comparable** to Standard DCB tests for the PW-RDL-RDC composites
- Welch's t-test on $G_{Plateau}$ values
- p-value: 0.57
- p-value > 0.05, **no statistically significant difference** in the mean fracture toughness at the 95% confidence level

Fatigue Testing of HTDCB

Loading-controlled vs Displacement-controlled Fatigue

Fracture toughness equation for HTDCB

Load-controlled fatigue → "Simplified Version",

$$G_I = \frac{12 P^2 a^2}{E h_o^3 (1 + ka)^3 b^2} + \frac{P^2}{k_s G h_o (1 + ka) b^2}$$

Compliance, $C = \frac{\delta}{P}$

Displacement-controlled fatigue →

$$G_I = \frac{12 \left(\frac{\delta}{C}\right)^2 a^2}{E h_o^3 (1 + ka)^3 b^2} + \frac{\left(\frac{\delta}{C}\right)^2}{k_s G h_o (1 + ka) b^2}$$

1. To be conservative, **90% $G_{plateau}$**
2. **A-basis allowable** = Mean of plateau load – 3 * Standard deviation = **720 N**

P_{max}	720 N	δ_{max}	8.0 mm
P_{min}	72 N	δ_{min}	0.8 mm

- **ΔG remains constant under load-controlled fatigue**, whereas it **decreases** progressively under **displacement-controlled fatigue**.
- HTDCB **fatigue testing** should be conducted under **force control** to maintain a constant ΔG during crack growth.

HTDCB Fatigue Testing: Proof of Concept

- Load-controlled fatigue
- Load ranges: 55 N to 550 N
- Fatigue frequency = 1 Hz
- $\Delta G/G_{plateau} = 65\%$
- $65\% \text{ of } G_{plateau} \text{ (A basis allowable)} = 1080 \text{ J/m}^2$
- Crack was propagated quasi-statically until the crack tip reached the plateau region

HTDCB Fatigue Testing: Proof of Concept

Mode-I Fatigue Test
Instrumentation

- Stable fatigue crack growth

Conclusion

- **Deflection and compliance equations** were derived using **Timoshenko Beam Theory**, incorporating both **flexural and shear effects**.
- **LEFM-based SERR equation (G)** was derived and validated against ASTM D3433-99 for metal joints.
- **Parametric analysis** identified a **5° taper angle with a 75 mm** initial crack length as optimal among the 0°–10° range.
- Quasi-static testing of HTDCB showed **R-curve behavior** comparable to Standard DCB for PW-RDL-RDC composites.
- **Load increased** during the **R-curve region** and **plateaued** after reaching **stable fracture toughness**.
- R-curve behavior resulted from mechanisms including **fiber bridging, tow-to-tow delamination, and secondary cracking**.
- **Stable fatigue crack growth** was achieved at 65% of G_{IC}
- HTDCB configuration ensured **ΔG remains independent of crack growth** during fatigue testing.

Ongoing Work

- Establish a Fatigue Delamination Model for Mode I Fatigue of Plain Weave S-glass Epoxy
- Growth of delamination damage in composite laminates is conventionally described by a Paris-law type of relation given below:

$$\frac{da}{dN} = C \left(\frac{\Delta G}{G_c(a)} \right)^m$$

- Validation of Fatigue Delamination Model using Standard DCB Specimen
- Establish a Cohesive Zone Model (CZM) based on Fatigue Delamination Model (or Paris Law) for Mode I Fatigue of Plain Weave S-glass Epoxy Composite
- This approach can potentially be applied for characterizing Mode II and mixed-mode (I/II) fatigue delamination behavior

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Questions?

